

ISic0698

I.Sicily inscription 0698

Language

Latin

Type

calendar

Material

marble (grey)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

These fragments are now united with the other Taormina fragments and forms part of ISic0662 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0662>] , as argued by Ruck 1996 and are now on display in Tauromenium

Digital identifiers:

TM 493944

EDCS 32701133

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 166 no.28

Ruck, B. 1996. Die fasten von Taormina. *ZPE*. 111: 271-280. At 271 n.7

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